

St. Nicholas of Melissourgoi

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Entry tags: Cathedral, Christianity, Archaeological Site, Greece, Basilica, Religious Group, Abrahamic, Church, Greek, Language, Religious Place, Epirus, Orthodox Christianity, Balkans, Orthodoxy

St. Nicholas is the main church of the village Melissourgoi of Arta in Greece. The church was originally built in the second half of the 18th century. It was burned by the Ottomans in 1821 and by Nazi troops in WWII.

Date Range: 1778 CE - 1967 CE

Region: Melissourgoi Artas

Region tags: Greece

A mountainous area in the Pindos mountains, named Tzoumerka.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

The society in which the religious place is located is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Notes: But it commemorates them.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Were the structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Thanksgiving to a god/gods for favor received

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Type of elevation

– Rock face

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Notes: The village of Melissourgoi, Arta.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Plantings

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Has this place been looted:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL

– Source 1 Description

– Source 2 URL

– Source 2 Description

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ A group of features:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ A single structure

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ One single feature

– Mound

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ In antiquity

– Periodically

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Worship:

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Earth

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Sand

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Clay

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Grass

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Stone

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Lime

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the inscriptions a formal dedication:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: Frescoes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Angels

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: As a part of the wooden altar

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Notes: By the famous Chioniadites painters.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Iconography

Are there distinct features of the iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Humans

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Notes: It commemorates the dead ritually.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Supernatural Beings

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

In waking, everyday life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

In dreams:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Only through a monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is a supreme high god present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Do they have another type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Do they have kin relation with elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ other:

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Supernatural Interactions

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

Notes: Through prayer.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Other:

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Sacred objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Daily life objects:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify

Notes: A few years back, daily.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Bloodless ritual sacrifices in the Divine Liturgy.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are festivals present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Institutions and Scriptures

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Function for water management:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Part of the transportation network:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Other

– Other [specify]

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Religious Specialists

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: Metropolis of Arta

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Present full time

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Present part time

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Bureaucracy

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Melissourgoi, Epirus

Bibliography

General References

Reference: St. Nicholas of Melissourgoi, Makris, Kitsos. Χιονιάδίτες ζωγράφοι 65 λαϊκοί ζωγράφοι από το χωριό χιονιάδες της ηπείρου. Athens, Greece: Melissa Publications, 1981.